

Musical Aspects of 'Mallari' : with special reference to the traditions at Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple

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Abstract

For many centuries, temples in India have not only been places of worship, but also seats of learning, which played an important role in the preservation and development of fine arts. Music in its Triple aspects of Gita, Vadya and Nritya (Vocal music, Instrumental Music and Dance) was given a prominent place in temple rituals. Worship through music was a way of life and unique music traditions in some temples of South India evolved. 'Mallari' is a musical form belonging to Temple Music played on the Nagaswaram and Thavil, which are distinct musical instruments of the temple and are customarily played during all ritualistic worship of deities and ceremonial processions of God within the temple premises. Ritualistic performances of Mallari were a communication tool between people and the temple in the olden days, which had an impact on the socio-cultural lives of people. In this research that I conducted as a participatory observant, I wish to present the varied types of melodic and rhythmic dimensions of this musical form with an analysis of the performance mode of Mallari in comparison with the present day performance of 'Pallavi' in Ragam-Tanam-Pallavi aspect of Manodharma Sangeetam.

Keywords : Mallari, Temple Music, Ritualistic Music, Nagaswaram, Thavil, Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple

Research Paper

Introduction

Mallari is instrumental music played only on the Nagaswaram. There is a set of *Solkattu*^[1] set to particular patterns of *Svaras*. This pattern is played on the instrument as a tune and on the Thavil in the form of *Jati-s*. According to many Musicians, Mallari has been played since the time Temples existed. Mallari, the most popular musical style among them, is being played in South Indian States as a musical form in the 35 *Suladi Sapta Tala-s*. The Agamic and other ritual texts speak in detail about the musical offerings to be made in Temples.

Tyagaraja temple at Tiruvarur is one of the most ancient heritage sites in India. The Glory of this temple complex is sung in more number of devotional hymns from *Thiruvachgam* (353) written by a number of *Nayanmars*—Tamil Saiva Saints of 7th century and later periods.

Bari Nagaswaram is one of rarest instruments specifically attached to Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple. It is only played

for Lord Tyagaraja and Goddess Kamalamba and not to other Gods and Goddesses outside Tiruvarur. This *Bari Nagaswaram* of Tiruvarur is continuously being played by the same family of artists for about 24 generations now at the Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple (Palaniappan). Here, Lord Shiva in the form of Tyagaraja whose cosmic dance is popular and is famous for the *Ajapa natanam* (dance without chanting); god himself executes this move. Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple also has two secrets similar to Chidambaram Natarajar temple. First one is the hidden body of Tyagaraja and the second is *Ajapa natanam*.

Methodology

This is a Qualitative Research and I used structured and semi-structured interviews to collect information from Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple Asthana Vidwan Sri Palaniappan. As a part of my field work, I collected primary data like Notations and Recordings of Mallari being traditionally rendered by artistes, who have

been a part of the ritualistic temple traditions, for the past 24 generations. My secondary data sources are the books that I had taken from Madurai Sadguru Sangeeta Vidyalaya and Tanjavur Tamil University. I was a participant observant in the field, where I travelled along with them observing their patterns of playing the musical form, accompanying them on the Sruti.

Mallari

Mallari is a musical form played in Nagaswaram for the temple rituals only. It is a unique composition and there are many other types of this composition. Some scholars express it as *Mayil + Aari = Mallari*. Mallari's vocabulary is similar to that of peacock. "Aari" in Tamil means 'making sound or singing'. Currently, there is a procession of Lord Tyagaraja and some sort of vehicle is utilized. In the past, only members of the 'Mallar' lineage were permitted to host the swami. So, some scholars believe this statement (Biju). For performing rituals like 'Abhishekam' (holy bath of Lord) and 'Veedhi Purappattu' (procession of Lord on street), 'Nivedana' (food offering to Lord) etc., Mallari is played. Mallari is usually played in Gambhiranata as the Raga stands for Veera Rasa. Mallari typically has no *sahithyam* (lyrics).

Classification of Mallari

There are two major classifications of Mallari - Chinna Mallari and Periya Mallari.^[2] While Chinna Mallari can be played on all days, Periya Mallari can be played only on specific days. 'Ther' (Chariot) Mallari is mainly done in Khanda Jathi. This is only performed for god. It does not honour any gurus or rulers. The lord is taken in procession on the streets while Mallari is performed. This is readily apparent practically at all temple functions.

As per tradition during the Temple Rituals, there also prevailed a special pattern for temple processions, the most important being the rendition of Mallari. During processions and whenever *Deeparadhana* (worship of lamp) was performed, Nagaswaram and the Thavil together as an ensemble played a compositional type, predominantly in Raga Gambhiranata, called Mallari. This practice continues even today (Sethuraman).

It was Muthuswami Dikshitar's father, Ramaswami Dikshitar who formalised the Utsava Rituals in the Tiruvarur temple and specified the stages of Mallari to be played during the daily pooja and Annual festivals (Ghilgith). This was a custom followed by all the Nagaswara vidwans at the temple. Mallari is at present predominantly performed in Tamil Nadu state and might be there in the boundaries of Kerala state

(Ernakulam and Kochi, Alappuzha, Kodungallur) and Andhra Pradesh (Tirumala Tirupati Devasthanams i.e., Aragimpu Mallari). Nonetheless, many have started to perform Mallari in Bharathanatyam, these days.

Reason for using Gambhiranata Raga

Mallari is typically played only in the Gambhiranata raga (Lecture), though some musicians have also composed it in different Raga-s and Tala-s. Some reasons why Mallari is associated with this raga are given below:

- ❖ Gambhiranata Raga consists of 5 svara in the Audava-Audava format.
- ❖ As a general principle, Agamas says that everything that is referring to God (shiva) must be related to the number 5 like how, the Gambhiranata Raga has 5 *Svaras* (Audava Raga or Pentatonic Scale). Lord shiva, has 5 faces that is Sadyojata, Isana, Agora, Vamadeva and Tatpurusa.^[3]
- ❖ In Some Siva temples there are five *Prakaras*, with five steps that lead to the Sanctum Sanctorum.
- ❖ The Importance of the number 5 is also extended to the five elements where the worship of Siva is seen.
- ❖ An observation related to the *Veera Rasa* can also be made where the People belonging to Mallar community make use of this Rasa while carrying the Palanquin on their shoulders, to lessen the pain and to move forward in an enthusiastic way similarly to how Soldiers carry their king happily in a Procession. While hearing Mallari people can feel the enthusiasm and freshness of melody and rhythm.

Every Mallari often begins with Nagaswara Vidwan playing Gambhiranata Ragam before the Thavil Performer plays Alarippu in the Khanda Nada. Mallari is then recited according to the Rhythmic type.

Types of Mallari-s

In addition to the Mallari-s of older times, there are newly added Mallari-s, making a total of 16 types :

1. Theertha Mallari
2. Thaligai Mallari
3. Kadam or Kumbha Mallari
4. Ther Mallari
5. Tiruputa Tala Mallari
6. Sapta Tala Mallari (This 6th mallari has seven mallari-s classified under it. Since each is of a different type of Tala, these are called in term "Sapta tala").

7. Dhruva Tala Mallari
8. Matya Tala Mallari
9. Rupaka Tala Mallari
10. Jhampa Tala Mallari
11. Triputa Tala Mallari
12. Ata Tala Mallari
13. Eka Tala Mallari
14. Pancha Nada Mallari
15. Talamaligai Mallari
16. Anga Tala Mallari
17. Pancharatna Mallari or (Ragamalika Mallari)

Mallari-s played in Tiruvarur Temple

- ❖ Theertha Mallari
- ❖ Nivedana Mallari^[4]
- ❖ Purappattu Mallari (It consists of 6 Mallari - Purappattu Mallari means, it can be played when God is taken through streets of praakaram or outside the temple)
- ❖ Tiruputa Tala Mallari
- ❖ Khanda Mallari
- ❖ Sapta Tala Mallari
- ❖ Pancha Nada Mallari
- ❖ Ther Mallari
- ❖ Ajapanatana Mallari

Nivedana Mallari

Talam:- Khanda Jati Eka Talam

Total no of akshara in one avarta= 20

P P P S P	P P S P P	P P , S S	S P S S P
S S P S S	P S S S S	P S S S S	P S S S S
P P P P S	P P S S P	S S P P P	S P P P S

Thavil Taththakaram

Thom thom thom thath thom thom thom thath thom thath thom thom tha tha tha

Thom tha tha thom that tha thom tha that tha tha thom thatha tha thom

Ta ta ta Thom thom thom thom tha thom thom thatha thom tha tha

Thom thom thom tha thom thom thom tha.

Nivedana Mallari is played daily in the Evening - 5.50 pm to 6.00 pm, starting in *Mandra Sthayi Pancama* (lower Octave P). It is mostly rendered from *Mandra sthayi* to *Madhya sthayi*. In this Mallari only two notes are played.

In the Nivedana Mallari, played during Sri Latchappa Pillai (1926)period(Saminathan Interview). They played Nivedana Mallari in Misra Jati Triputa Talam.^[5]

Tala:- Misra Jathi Tisra Triputa - Total no of akshara in one avarta = 49

P,,P,,,	P,,S,,,	P,,P,,,		P,,S,,,	P,,S,,,		G,,S,,,	G,,S,,,	
G,,S,,NN	S,,G,,SN	NS,G,,SN		NSP,,P,	,,P,,,,		.P,,P,,	.S,,,,,	³

Now, it is not followed because there is no *Asthana Vidwan* for Thavil in this Temple. The tradition slowly disappeared after Latchappa Pillai.

Purappattu Mallari

Tripuda Tala Mallari or Vezhli Purappattu Mallari

Talam:- Tripuda Tala - Total no of akshara in one avarta= 8

Madhyama kala:-

P , N P | S N | S , ||
 G S S , | , , | N P ||
 S N S , | G S | S , ||
 P , N P | S N | P P ||

N P S N | P P | N , ||
 P P S , | P N | SG SN ||
 S , , , | P N | SG SN ||
 S , , , | P N | SG SN ||

Druta kala:-

P , NP SNS, GSS, ; NP | SNS, GSS, | P, NP SNPP ||
 NP SN PP N, PPS, P NSGSN | S, ; P NSGSN | S, ; P NSGSN ||⁴

Prahaara Purappattu Mallari

Talam:- Misra Jhampa

Total no of akshara in one avarta=10

Madhyama kala:-

P , P , N , P | , | P , ||
 S , S , G , S | G | SG SN ||
 P , P , N , P | , | P , ||
 S , , , , , , | , | SG SN ||

Druta kala:-

P, P, N, P, P, S, S, | G, | SG SGS N ||
 P, P, N, P, P, S, ; | ; | ; SGS N ||⁵

Prahaara purappattu mallari, is recited from the first Praharam to Kodi Maram (flag hoist).

Khanda Mallari or Veedhi Purappattu Mallari

Talam:- Khanda Jati Tripuda

Total no of akshara in one avarta = 9

Madhyama kala:-

P , , P , | , P | S , ||
 , P S , N | S G | S N ||
 P S N S , | G M | P , ||
 S N P , P | M G | S N ||

S G M P , | P , | G M ||
 P N S G M | G S | N S ||
 , P N S N | P M | G M ||
 P , N P P | M G | S N ||

Druta kala:

P , , P ; P S ; P S , NSG SNPS |
 NS, G MP, S | NP, P MGSN ||

SGMP , P, G MPN S G MG S N S , P |
 NSN P MGMP | , NP P MGSN ||⁶

Ther Mallari is played during the chariot festival while the chariot is being pulled. For intimating to the public, it is mostly rendered in Khanda Gati Adi Tala. In most of the cases the same Ther Mallari is followed all over the district.

But in Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple, Ther Mallari has some unique specialisations. Two Main Temples famous for Mallari, are Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple and Chidambaram Nataraja Temple. In the same way Mallari in Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple is more ancient than others. Normally Mallari has no *sahithyam*. But, in this Temple tradition Ther Mallari has *Sahithyam* for praising the god (Pazhaniappan). It's a two *Avartha* Mallari and starts at *Mandra Pancama*. The *Sahithyam* is –

“Tyagaraja Sri Tyagaraja Aaroora Tyagesha” [8]

During the Chariot festival all the people chant the words “Aaroora Tyagesha” out of devotion for God. This might be the reason why the words “Aaroora Tyagesha” are included in the *sahithyam*. The Chariot takes a turn while entering the next street in four *Mada veedhi* (streets) in Tiruvarur. Ther Mallari is played at this turn. The whole day, Ther Mallari is played and in between they also play some *Krti*-s and *Varnam*-s. While playing Ther Mallari *Bari Nagaswaram* is accompanied by *Kodukotti*[9] and *Talam* (Bhairavi). The person-s who play these three instruments will be sitting on the Chariot.

During the chariot festival *Bari Nagaswaram* is played in front of the chariot before and during the departure after the Veda chant summoning to play *Bari Nagaswaram* and every time the green flag is displayed during the course of the chariot ride.

The chariot goes round about the four streets immediately outside the temple in a circular motion roughly. So, at the end of each street when the chariot turns to the next street, the *Ther Mallari* (a type of the compositional type mallari) is played.

In the festival, *Azhi Ther* (Big Chariot) moves very slowly. There is a proverb where slow walking is compared to the Tiruvarur Chariot (In Tamizh)– “Tiruvarur Ther pola nadakkatha”.

Infact, this chariot is not a normal one. It is very huge in size and weighs a lot. 30 years back Tiruvarur chariot weighed more compared to the contemporary one. Because of its weight, it took a very long time to pull the chariot. Those days chariot festival ran for 3 days.

There are two major reasons for the reduction of the chariot's weight. Firstly, due to people's busy schedules these days, they can't afford more time for the festival.

Second, development and construction of huge buildings on both sides of the streets necessitated the reduction of the Chariot's weight.

Earlier, Mallari used to be played for three days. The Musicians used to improvise the two *Avartha*-s daily without any repetition. At the same time, people valued the Mallari as much as the festival. But these days Mallari is played only for a day and no attention is paid to the Music or the Musicians. During one of my interactions with the Musicians, he said that no one actually notices the Musicians in the Chariot Festival.

The Musicians create the *Svara* Patterns in sync with the movements of the Chariot (Swaminathan Interview). This creation of the Music is based on their *Manodharma Sangita*. In this Mallari improvisation is done in accordance to the chariot movement. Musicians create *svara* pattern adding each *Avartam* starting and ending like the Chariot movement.

In Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple, they had some specific and rare featured Mallari which are played only in *Bari Nagaswaram*. And, the unique thing is that in this temple it is not played in *Trisra* nor even the *Dhruta kala*.^[10] The Musician increases the tempo while playing i.e., *Nivedhana* Mallari is started in 60 tempo, then they increased it to 120 tempo. This method is followed in Tiruvarur Thygaraja Temple (Pazhaniappan).

Every year in Tiruvarur Tyagaraja Temple, the Ther festival is held with great fanfare and the Ther Mallari is traditionally done. Ther Mallari is played when the Swamy departs. Even today in the same way Ther Mallari is recited with the same tradition. Similarly three Mallari-s are being played in Tyagaraja temple as part of the tradition since decades. *Nivedana* Mallari, *Prahara Purappattu* Mallari-s and *Ther Mallari* (Pazhaniappan). In this temple mallari is being played with the exact notation and gradually raise in tempo. *Kumbha* Mallari was performed during *kumbhabhishekam*, and the majority of temples presented Ther Mallari during the *kumbhabhishekam*.

Pirahara Purappattu Mallari is played in 22 days festivals. 13th day of the yearly Festival honouring Lord Chandrasekhar because, he's the one who has to get the right to conduct the Chariot festival. At that time, Ther Mallari is played for Chandrasekhara in *vasantha mandapam* there are nine steps to the *vasantha mandapam*. Before that, while going from the first *Praharam* to the second *Praharam*, *Nivedana* Mallari is recited. In the present day, only three Mallari-s are played at Tyagaraja Temple.

Pancha Nada Mallari

Pancha nada mallari was played in Tyagaraja temple for the swami procession. Pancha Nada Mallari means changing the Nada (When tempo of the tala is changed from pattern to another pattern, its called Gati Bhedam). But, now it is not followed in this temple(Saminathan Interview).

Analysis

Mallari is a form of music played on Nagaswaram, the Mangala vadyam (auspicious instrument) and this performance is an important part of Nagaswaram repertoire. Music played on Nagaswaram is an important part of the day to day temple rituals, where it is usually accompanied on the Thavil. Earlier, the concept of concerts in temples was very different from the existing pattern. Ragas were rendered with aesthetics of sruti and laya, with a judicious mix of embellishments and appropriate to the worship of the presiding deity.

Earlier, ragas handled for Mallari presentation was mainly Gambhiranata and the others were in Ghana raga-s. The notation of Mallari was limited in range and also number of svara-s, and a variety in svara and laya structures was practised. In the present day, the practise of presenting Varnam-s, Keertana-s, Javali-s, Thillana-s in Nagaswaram concerts has evolved and thus there has been a development and change in the concert format from the earlier raga-oriented approach to the present format of handling modern musical forms.

In Ancient days, Mallari was played in *Madhyama Kala* and they only used to increase the tempo. After the Medieval period, artists started playing in different speeds. In the Present day, Mallari is played in Trisram, *Trisram Paikalam* (rendered 6 *Aksharas* per beat).

'Pallavi', one of the musical aspect of *Manodharma Sangitam*, is also in the same format. Pallavi is rendered in the Madhyama kala, Vilamba, Druta, Trisra, and a combination of various speeds and tempo-s. And some people are also playing Svarakalpana for Mallari. Pallavi has *sahithya*. But, Mallari has no *Sahithya* and it is completely based on Jathi Patterns. The Theme and Structure is different but the way of rendition is similar to the Musical form. So, Mallari can be considered as the ancestor of 'Pallavi'.

Mallari has more scope for tala variation. It is completely Mathematical oriented. Mallari can be built in any Tala, but mostly it is in Triputa Tala. Mallari has to be played in standing or walking position. But, in playing the Ther Mallari, they sit in the Chariot and play the Mallari.

Mallari has been prominently played in Nagaswaram and Thavil. In Tyagaraja Temple Ther Mallari is played accompanied by Kodu Katti. Tyagaraja temple has two secrets, first one is that swami body is hidden and second one is Ajapa natana. Ajapa natana mallari is played during the Ajapa natana dance. This Mallari represent the heart beat of Vishnu. But, now-a-days, this mallari is not played in this temple because of lack of skilled artists. In the improvisation of this mallari, the artist adds the swara like the blossoming of a lotus flower.

Results

History of Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple and its rituals, and the unique presentation and performances of Mallari on the Nagaswaram bring forth the speciality of the Mallari-s and the instrument used here, to limelight. All the artistes who have richly contributed to the evolution and development of the Mallari playing styles in Tiruvarur Tyagaraja temple have also been furnished which highlight the great living traditions existing in the temple. Also the presentation of Mallari music on 'Bari Nagaswaram', a rare instrument unique to this temple is a significant revelation.

Notations of various types of Mallari-s performed in the temple are analysed in detail, thus documenting the musical form for posterity to understand and explore this rich traditional repertoire of temple music.

This study also highlights the importance of nurturing this instrument and restoring the traditional practises of temples and its rich heritage. This will not only provide a livelihood for many artistes, but will also protect this endangered and ancient art. More opportunities should be created in restoring the employment of Nagaswaram and Thavil vidwans in many temples and also in establishing traditional teaching systems where the art can be imparted in its purest form, which will help us protect our cultural arts and ancient temple musical forms.

Conclusion

Mallari can be presented in 3 different ways *Gita*, *Vadya*, *Nrithya*. Svara or *Thathakaram* is used while singing Mallari. *Svara* is played on Nagaswaram and *Thathakaram* is played on Thavil. *Thaththakaram* Jathi is also used in Bharatanatyam. Ajapa Natana Mallari, Anga Tala Mallari and Thalamalika Mallari were played until 40 year-s ago. Now it is not played in this Temple. Mallari is a very scientifically laid down structure of raga-tala presentation which was not only appealing but also in keeping with the time of the day.

In olden days, Mallari was a communication tool between people and the ritual-s happening in the temple. The village folk could easily identify the time without clocks merely by listening to the ragas and the songs (Vedavalli). Devotees would also be able to know which pooja was being performed. This evidences the fine-tuned prayer scheme prevalent in south Indian temples. But now people lack the knowledge of this Mallari as they are not showing interest in these Musical forms because of their busy lives.

Acknowledgement

The authors heartily acknowledge Dr. Pragya Pyasi, Assistant Professor, Department of Music, University of Hyderabad, for her input and support for completing the article.

The authors also thank Sri Pazhaniappan Selvaganapathi, Temple Ashthana Vidwan, Tiruvarur Temple, ‘Thiruvavaduthurai Aadheenam Nagaswara Vidwan’ Prof. N.S. Saminathan, Professor in Violin, Sri Sathguru Sangeetha Vidyalayam, Madurai, Dr. S. Meenakshi, Flautist, Madurai and Ms. Bhairavi M SRF, Research Scholar, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Tiruvarur, for their inputs and kind support during my research.

Footnotes

1. ‘Solkattu’ is the art of spoken rhythmic syllables, literally meaning ‘syllables’ (sol) and ‘bunch’ (kattu)
2. Ther Mallari, Tripura Mallari and Misra Chapu Mallari altogether they are called Periya Mallari.
3. Sangita Sampradayam, Vedavalli R, volume 2
4. In the Siva sthala, it is called the Nivedana Mallari and in the Vishnu sthala, it is called Thaligai Mallari.
5. Saminathan, Interviewed about Mallari
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